

Environmental Rights, Values and Duties

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Introduction

Environmental values, rights and duties are closely interlinked. For the last few decades, there are serious concerns that are being voiced regarding the environmental degradation that is fast eroding the sustainability factor of the planet earth. There is reiteration of local cultures and customs that are environment-friendly. The movements for right to clear environment have gained momentum and along with them, the duties and values are now considered as crucial factors for protecting the precious natural resources. This article deals with a basic understanding of the environmental values, rights and duties.

“We stand at a critical moment in Earth’s history, a time when humanity must choose its future. As the world becomes increasingly interdependent and fragile, the future at once holds great peril and great promise. To move forward we must recognize that in the midst of a magnificent diversity of cultures and life forms we are one human family and one Earth community with a common destiny. We must join together to bring forth a sustainable global society founded on respect for nature, universal human rights, economic justice, and a culture, of peace. Towards this end, it is imperative that we, the peoples of Earth, declare our responsibility to one another, to the greater community of life, and to future generations”.

Of late, there has been an increasing level of consciousness towards protecting our environment and planet earth. Numerous conventions, conferences, debates and discussions are being conducted on this subject and topics like pollution, environmental degradation, soil erosion, deforestation, greenhouse effect and depletion of ozone layer etc. have been extensively discussed upon. The environmental groups, activists, academics and policy makers are now incessantly talking of clean environment and its importance for a healthy living. What constitutes this clean environment? What are the steps taken by the national and international organisations to ensure that we live in an environmentally healthy world? What are the basic rights regarding the environment that we are entitled to? And most importantly what are our duties in ensuring that our environment is clean and healthy?

An attempt has been made in this paper to answer some of the above questions and the dire need to maintain a clean environment for a healthy and sustainable living on this planet earth.

One of the pioneering steps towards addressing the issue of human environment was taken in 1972 with the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment at Stockholm. The Conference had evolved the principles and action plan for controlling and regulating the environmental degradation. The UN General Assembly called for the cooperation of various nation states in this endeavor and to take up the issues of environment in their respective countries for better environmental governance. Various national and international organisations have since come together for the protection and preservation of the environment. It also involved the national and international state agencies and civil society groups apart from the non-governmental organisations to undertake this massive task. Since then the concept of environmental governance had gained momentum and environmental governance had gained momentum and enormous efforts are now being undertaken to ensure the mankind's right to clean environment.

Right to Clean Environment

What constitutes a clean and healthy environment? In principle, it states that a healthy human environment is required to ensure a healthy living. This includes clean air, water, and soil/land that are free from the usage of toxic and other hazardous substances that threaten a healthy living. Every living being is entitled to this environment and every human being is entitled to basic public services that improve human health conditions. The states have an obligation to ensure the protection and preservation of environment and take necessary steps to implement this objective. Taking into consideration the interdependence of all living beings and the human dependence on a healthy environment, the right to clean environment is deemed as a necessary prerequisite for healthy living.

It is important to note that the above mentioned conference has recognized two significant principles; one Principle 1 of the Stockholm Declaration states thus: the fundamental right (for man) to freedom, equality, and adequate conditions of life, in an environment of quality that permits a life of dignity and well-being. Principle 7 of the Declaration laid the onus on the states to take steps to prevent pollution of the environment. Efforts were also undertaken under the aegis of the International Environmental Law to bring out laws on the protection of biodiversity, natural flora and fauna, endangered species, forest reserves, control of pollution, and drastically limiting the use of hazardous substances that threaten all living beings. The UN General Assembly, in its Resolution 45/94, categorically recognized that all individuals are entitled to healthy environment. The UN also created the position of Special Rapporteur on Human Rights and Environment, and came out with a report, popularly known as Ksentini Report. The Report presented a theoretical, thematic, and practical framework thus establishing an important link between human rights and environment.

The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights recognize an inherent right to life of every human being through attainment of highest standards of physical and mental health and through the improvement of all aspects of environmental and industrial hygiene. The Economic, Social and Cultural Rights also recognize the importance of a healthy environment, decent living conditions and health. All these establish a crucial link between healthy environment and human health. Among the International Charters related to be Human Rights, the African Charter of Human and people Rights (ACHPR, 1981) in its Article 24, recognizes the rights of all individuals to a satisfactory environment. Further, in Europe, the Organization of Economic and Cooperation and Development (OECD) the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) and the Organization of American States, in its 1988 Protocol of San Salvador have all directly or indirectly acknowledge the human right to a clean environment.

In India the Right to a clean environment has been overtly recognized in the Constitution of India, Part IV under the Directive Principles of the State Policy. In the forty Second Amendment Act of the Indian Constitution, 1976 the provision for environmental protection and improvement has been incorporated through the insertion of article 48A, as part of State Policy. It states that the state shall endeavor to protect and improve the environment and to safeguard forests and wildlife of the country. Article 51 A (g), that deals with the fundamental duties of the citizens, also casts a similar responsibility on every citizen to improve casts a similar responsibility on every citizen to improve the natural environment including forests, lakes, rivers, and wildlife and to have compassion for all living creatures.

It is interesting to note that the right to life under Article 21 of the Indian Constitution has been interpreted in a way that includes the right to the environment. Though there is no direct mention of any similar provision, it has been indirectly interpreted that a clean and healthy environment is an obvious requirement for a healthy living; in case of its violation, it amounts to threat to life that negates the Constitutional Provision of Right to Life as in Article 21. It has been one of the landmark judicial interpretations by the Indian Judiciary.

India employs a range of regulatory instruments to preserve and protect its natural resources. There are stated to be over 200 Central and State Statutes, which have atleast some concern with environmental protection, either directly or indirectly. In India, there is good number of laws pertaining to the environmental protection and preservation, some of them in tandem with the international conventions and declarations. The National Environmental Policy documents some of the policies and programmes aimed at environmental protection. However, there is an element of disappointment with the governmental agencies that have not effectively enforce the compliance to the laws and and statutory norms. In this regard, the Judiciary has given some of the most commendable judgements regarding the environmental protection and has even enabled the citizens to voice their concerns through Public Interest Litigations that bring the issues to the notice of the higher courts. As the awareness regarding the threats to environment increased manifold, various NGOs and civil society groups too are now actively engaged in contributing towards the environmental governance. All these reflect a positive development that environmental governance in India does not exclusively involve decisions made by signal entity, rather it demonstrates a much more diffuse level of responsibility for environmental governance.

As noted earlier, the non-compliance to the laws and statutory norms is one of the major issues concerning the environmental protection. Various development projects are being taken up at mammoth levels at the expense of the natural resource depletion. In many cases, the environmental impact assessments are a mere eyewash, with the clearances issued in favour of the governmental or developmental bodies. The most affected are urban areas, with expanding population, migration from rural and small town regions that lay enormous pressure on the urban resources. No urban development plan in India makes any specific provision for energy sources which would be cost effective, provide adequate access to energy even to the poor, and which could be produced and used in such a manner that it does not lead to an environmental degradation. The consequences have been disastrous with the threats to the environment looming large. It is in this context that the importance of environmental values is being debated.

Environmental Values

While much has been debated and discussed on the role of governmental, non-governmental, judicial and other agencies, inadequate attention has been paid to the role and responsibility of the citizens towards environmental cleanliness. Some of the individual contributions to the environmental threats include excessive use of personal transportation that increases the emission

levels, heavy usage of the energy consuming gadgets littering ones surroundings, untestable consumption levels increased domestic waste including e-waste, dumping of harmful and hazardous medical waste. Part this may be attributed to the affluence, possession and consumption of the materials goods, an exclusive standard of individual and collective achievement. It has been one of the significant trickle-down effects of liberalisation, where in the materialistic culture gripped the nation. The materialistic consumption is now being calculated as the measuring standard of human development, leaving behind the basic issues of health care, sanitation, and hygiene, which are much more crucial to human health.

Environmental ethics and values are closely related to our behavior in the conservation of nature. Values, as Bharucha notes, lead to a process of decision making which leads to action. For value education in relation to the environment, this process is learned through an understanding and appreciation of nature's oneness and the importance of its conservation. It is an intellectual code of behavior that regulates man's relationship with nature. It cannot be imposed by law but has to be articulated, systematized, codified and brought to the doorsteps of each and every individual. In this regard, the individual responsibility towards the environmental protection has been rather dismal. This stems partially from the lack of social awareness and partly from the lack of environment ethics, values and education. James Speth identifies two factors that are central to the environmental ethics the protection of their (people) own sake of the living communities that evolved here with us and our trusteeship of the earth's natural wealth and beauty for generations to come. He also contends that to realize such a future, societies will have to free themselves from a variety of pernicious habits of thought, including enchantment of limitless material expansion and what John Kenneth Galbraith has said the highly contrived consumption of an infinite variety of goods and services.

India has had a distinct civilization and culture that was very much in consonance with natural habitat. Nature (prakriti) was revered with utmost devotion and was known for its culture and spiritual heritage in protecting its environment. The above factors constitute an important element in sustaining the natural wealth but have been constantly neglected by the mankind. The western perception that nature and environment exists for the service of humanity has slowly crept into our society, thus promoting the values of unsustainable consumption and acquisitive materialism. Dwivedi rightly observes that culture and religions of the world can provide a solid foundation for changing people's attitudes on the preservation and on servation of the environment. World religions and cultures, particularly Oriental belief systems, do not inherently subscribe to the abuse and exploitation of Nature for material and selfish gain. Unfortunately, culture and no part of the world has remained immune from mankind's irreverence towards nature, an irreverence that has brought in its wake the destruction of our own habitat, our progeny and ourselves.

He also identifies that ethical values emanating from the world religions and cultures are some of the basic determinants of our behavior towards nature. Almost all the religions of the world have in a direct or indirect manner, referred to the protection of environment as a fundamental duty of the mankind. For example, cultivating the earth and planting trees is considered as an act of spiritual upliftment in Zoroastrian faith. Judaism speak of care and concern for other living beings on the earth; Hinduism believes in the existence of the divine in all its living forms and severly condemns any violence against the nature habitat. Similarly, the cultural moorings have also a positive impact on our environmental behavior. For example, some of the communities like Bishnois have a high regard for nature and animals and do not tolerate inflicting of harm on the living species. For people living in the hilly terrains, nature is an inseparable part of their life and do not subscribe to exploiting it for material gains and comforts. Regrettably these values are now being corroded owing to the external cultural influences. The traditional environmental ethos is being replaced

by the current trends of western maternalism and consumerism. The concept of what is morally right or wrong changes from time to time, with these, there is an automatic change in our behavior patterns. There is also an ensuring change in the value systems that affect the holistic perspective a similar change is now being witnessed in our perception of the nature and environment. Nature, once valued and revered, is at the receiving end of the changing human behavior patterns, now attuned to the materialistic culture. As discussed earlier, we are all entitled to a clean environment. At the same time, we are also under obligation to fulfill certain prime duties to ensure the same.

Duties towards Clean Environment

Science and Technology have changed the course of our lives in an unprecedented manner. While it is perceived as the cause of the current state of environmental degradation, it is also viewed as an effective way to combat the environmental degradation through environmental friendly technology. It needs to be noted that we cannot formulate solutions through technological means alone. There is a need for a change in the way individuals think about and interact with their environment..if respect for environment is to be active and an ecological crisis averted. It has to be remembered that.

1. Development does not connote material culture and its enjoyment.
2. Human beings do not have the right to harm other forms of life and
3. Human beings cannot conquer nature for individual gains.

Our rights need to conform with our duties. All the religions of the world stress upon the individual's responsible behavior towards the environment therefore we have an obligation to sustain our natural resources and ensure their judicious usage. An ethical strategy for environmental conservation has been effectively spelt out in the first draft of the report on the World Conservation Strategy for the 1990s.

1. People should respect nature, like all creatures we are an integral part of nature as well as users and consumers of nature.
2. Every life form is unique and warrants respect regardless of its worth to people.
3. All persons should take responsibility for their impacts on nature.
4. People should ensure the means of survival of all other life forms and should not knowingly cause the extinction of another species.
5. People should treat all creatures humanely and protect them from cruelty and avoidable suffering.

As rational human beings, we have specific duties towards our humanity and God's creation. As Dwivedi explains these are categorized as manava dharma and global dharma (Here the term adharma refers to one's sense of duty and conformity to the moral law). While the concept of rights of all specifically connotes the former, the latter is extended to our compassion for all living beings on this earth. From here emanates the concept of vasudhaivakutumbakam, encompassing an expanded vision of our co-existence with all living beings as part of one family. Our moral duty, therefore, obligates us to view and treat all with compassion; this in essence, is our manavadharma. As **Mahatma Gandhi once said, our consumption should be need based and not greed based.** His saying thoroughly conforms with the manava dharma dimension; he forewarned us to voluntarily reduce our wants so that there is less consumption of resources in individual terms. Our sense of duty enables us to gain mastery over our basic human characteristics of greed and exploitation and also enables us to discipline our inner thoughts. This in turn, reinforces our values and ethics that are necessary to create an ecologically sound and sustainable order. We need to strongly inculcate in ourselves and our society to follow an ethical code of conduct towards protecting our environment. Some of the features include our determination to (1) work towards protection

of nature (2) Judiciously use the natural resource (3) protect the sanctity of nature. (4) Morally commit to sustainable consumption; (5) responsible be have towards environmental management.

On a note of individual responsibility we can promote an effective transition to sustainable society by educating ourselves and other, by fulfilling the societal obligations to use resources with care and most importantly by recognizing the fact that the future generations too are entitled to the resources, which we are depleting at an alarming rate. On a concluding note, we need to remember a crucial aspect as spelt out in The Earth Charter preamble.

“We must decide to live with a sense of universal responsibility, identifying ourselves with the whole Earth community as well as our local communities. We are at once citizens of different nations and of one world in which the local and global are linked. Everyone shares responsibility for the present and future well-being of the human family and the larger living world. The spirit of human solidarity and kinship with all life is strengthened where we live with reverence for the mystery of being, gratitude for the gift of life, and humility regarding the human place in nature”.

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